

Breeding male sterile rice lines with droopy leaves

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RGS20 is an ideal donor in developing male sterile lines with droopy leaves. It was crossed with leading maintainers having erect leaves. Results confirmed

that a single recessive gene controls the droopy leaf trait.

In F_2 , B_1F_2 and B_2F_2 , the droopy-leaf plants with the desired characters were selected and backcrossed to erect-leaf B lines to identify droopy-leaf B lines. The droopy leaf trait was then incorporated into a wild abortive (WA) background by backcrossing to the droopy B. Some promising droopy leaf male sterile lines

with WA cytoplasm and improved agronomic traits were released in 1990.

Panicles of the droopy leaf A line are all located in the upper leaves, which favors the receipt of foreign pollen. Thus, more hybrid rice seed can be produced with less effort by using the droopy-leaf male sterile lines because producers do not have to cut flag leaves and spray gibberellin. ■

Suspension initiation in indica rice requires proline

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Suspension cultures are frequently used as starting material for protoplast isolation. We manipulated the suspension initiation medium to produce a fast-growing embryogenic line needed for successful protoplast culture.

Dehulled IR72 seeds were sterilized in 70% vol/vol ethanol for 1 min and 2.62% vol/vol sodium hypochlorite. They were inoculated in a plastic petri dish (100 × 15 mm) containing 20 ml modified MS medium for callus induction. The cultures were incubated in the dark at 25 ± 1 °C for 3 wk. Calli were subcultured for 2 wk before suspension initiation.

We selected the friable, smooth, light yellow calli (the group of densely cytoplasmic cells as observed in an inverted microscope) to initiate suspension. About 2 g calli were placed in a 125-ml Erlenmeyer flask containing 30 ml liquid medium. We used two sets of basal medium, N6 and R2. Each set

Effect of proline on the initiation of suspension in indica rice. With proline: a) Prolific growth of secondary calli. b) Separation of microcalli from MC.

Without proline: c) Poor initiation of secondary calli. d) Unsustained growth of secondary calli. e) Necrotic MC in N_6P_0 , R_2P_0 ; light yellow, smooth, friable microcalli in N_6P_{10} , R_2P_{10} 8 wk after initiation; finer microcalli in about 20-wk-old suspension in N_6P_5 .